

Vocational Identity Among Students of Senior Secondary Schools in East District of Sikkim

Manita Sharma¹ & Anju Verma²

1. MA Student, Department of Education, Sikkim University
2. Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Sikkim University

Received : 28/04/2024 1st BPR : 08/05/2024 2nd BPR : 16/05/2024 Accepted : 24/05/2024

Abstract

Vocational Identity is one of the major component of agentic control which one has over his/her career development. Through vocational identity, a framework can be determined for setting up goals and self-direction. It also contributes to an individual's adjustment and well-being along with facilitating the transition which one goes through from school to work. Making a choice with respect to one's career is one of the most important aspects in one's life. The present paper aims to study the vocational identity among senior secondary school students of east district of Sikkim. The sample of the present study consist of 120 randomly selected senior secondary school students from east district of Sikkim. The descriptive survey method has been used to conduct this study. Vocational Identity scale developed by F. Veiga and Moura (2005) has been used in the study for collection of data. Descriptive and inferential has been used to analyse and interpret the data. To find out the difference between variables t-test was used. The result revealed no significant difference between male and female students of senior secondary school in relation to the variable Vocational Identity.

Keywords: Vocational Identity, Descriptive, inferential.

Introduction

In the Present world technology plays an important role in creating new opportunities by bringing about rapid technical and scientific changes in an individual's place of employment. Making a choice with respect to one's career is one of the most important aspects in one's life. Factors such as one's emotional strength, pressure exerted by the family, conforming to society's standards and knowledge about the vocational choices regarding various professions also influence one's ability in making a career-related decision. Adolescence is a period of transition having both long term and short term effects as both physical and psychological changes which are taking place within them in a rapid pace. During this transition, an individual's mind is often laced with confusion in attaining a sound judgment for any judgement. Erikson (1968) describes it as a crisis of identity versus role confusion, as the individual is on the threshold of deciding his future course both regarding personal life and vocational aspects also. The vocational choice is one of the major concern for them. If a person does not choose his occupation according to his potentialities and personality, his adjustment will be adversely affected. Therefore, the decision related to the selection of v ocation becomes one of the most important factor for the adolescent's future prospects.

Vocational Identity is one of the major component of agentic control which one has over his/her career development. Through vocational identity, a framework can be determined for setting up goals and self-direction. It also contributes to an individual's adjustment and well-being along with facilitating the transition which one goes through from school to work.

Erik H. Erikson's theory of psychosexual development (1968) along with the theory of life span development plays an important role for shaping the concept of vocational identity and they also have

a major implication on career development theories, concepts and stages. Erikson explained identity as one can understand who he is, his sense of personal control, freedom along with a coherence, consistency and harmony between the individual belief's, values and commitment. A person faces the situation of identity crisis when he/she has to choose the future path for themselves on their own. Erikson referred occupational identity as one of the central domain of an individual's identity formation. Vocational identity helps individual to develop their values, beliefs and commitment towards work and to assists an adolescent in finding commitment to education, work and vocation.

It is very much beneficial to understand the process of vocational identity, for this purpose career counselors in school can evaluate an individual's abilities, interests, talents and personality characteristics and combine them to make the students realize academic and career goals and they can utilize their time in selecting good vocations. Guidance programme in schools for students can be provided to know the capability of the child. This study focuses on the scientific basis to formulate appropriate strategies for vocational development of adolescents. Therefore, it is required to study the vocational identity among senior secondary school students of East District of Sikkim. Hence the present study was conducted with the following objectives:

Objectives

1. To find out the level of Vocational Identity among male and female students of secondary schools
2. To compare the Vocational Identity among male and female students of Senior Secondary schools.

Hypotheses

Ho1. There is no significant difference between male and female Senior Secondary school students in relation to vocational identity.

Method

In the present study descriptive survey method was adopted, where the questionnaire was distributed to the students and their responses were gathered to examine the vocational identity among senior secondary school students of east district of Sikkim.

Population and Sample

The population in the present study comprised of the total senior secondary school students studying in class XI and XII senior secondary school students of east district of Sikkim. The total size of the sample is 120 (60 Males and 60 Females) selected from 6 schools (3 Government and 3 Private) from east district of Sikkim. In order to select the sample of the study the 'Random Sampling Technique' has been used as a sampling technique

Tool Used

For the present study "Vocational Identity scale" was used which was developed by F. Veiga and Moura (2005)

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

For analyzing quantitative data at first the data was organized and then the analysis was done by using appropriate statistics and at last the interpretation of the result is being prepared using tables and figures.

Levels of Vocational Identity among male and female students of senior secondary school based on Vocational Identity Scale.

To study the differential level of Vocational Identity among students of Senior Secondary schools they were divided and categorized under five different levels (very good, poor, average, good and very good). These are shown in the following Table- 1:

Table-01

Percentage of Male and Female students of
Senior Secondary Schools on level of Vocational Identity

Range of Scores	Description	Male	Percentage	Female	Percentage
140 - 113	Very Good	5	8.3%	7	11.7%
112 - 85	Good	51	85%	51	85%
84 - 57	Average	4	6.7%	2	3.3%
56 - 29	Poor	0	0%	0	0%
28 - 0	Very Poor	0	0%	0	0%

It is evident from the above Table -1 that from the total sample of the students of senior secondary school's male have (8.3%) and females have (11.7%) very good level and male (85%) and female (85%) have good level of Vocational Identity. While very few male (6.7%) and Female (3.3%) have average level and male (0%) and female (0%) have poor and very poor level of Vocational Identity. Therefore, it can be said that the majority of the Male and Female students of senior secondary School have good Vocational Identity. The levels are shown in the below Fig. 1:

Fig. 1

Bar Diagram representing the level of Vocational Identity among male and female students of Senior Secondary schools.

Analysis for the Significance difference between mean scores of male and female students of senior secondary schools on the variable of Vocational Identity.

H₀₁ states, there is no significant difference between male and female students of senior secondary schools in relation to their Vocational Identity.

To find out the difference among male and female students of senior secondary schools in relation to Vocational Identity and to test the above hypothesis, an independent sample two-tailed *t*-test has been conducted. The result of the test has been given in Table-2:

Table -2 Results of *t*-test examining the difference between male and female students of senior secondary schools in relation to the variable of Vocational Identity.

Variable	Male(60)		Female(60)		t (118)	P
	M	SD	M	SD		
Vocational Identity	101.3	9.84	101.8	9.84	0.28	0.77

**Significant at 0.05 level

*Table value of 't' at 0.05 level is 1.98

For overall Vocational Identity it is evident from the above table -2 of an independent sample two-tailed *t*-test that there is no significant difference between male and female students of senior secondary schools in relation to the Vocational Identity ($t(118)=0.28, P=0.77$).

Hence the mentioned null hypothesis "There is no significant difference between male and female students of senior secondary schools in relation to the variable of Vocational Identity" is accepted. The mean scores of male and female are shown in the below Fig-2

Fig. 2

Bar graph depicting mean scores on Vocational Identity among male and female students of senior secondary schools.

Findings

From the analysis it was found that the majority of the Male and Female students of senior secondary Schools have good level of Vocational Identity and There is no significant difference between male and female students of senior secondary school in relation to the variable of Vocational Identity

Conclusion

In present technological era the students are facing difficulties while taking decisions regarding their career. The decision related to the selection of the right vocation becomes an important challenge for the student's future. If anyone choses the occupation not according to his potentialities and personality the overall adjustment will be adversely effected. When the choice of a career will be made on realistic professional aspiration, complete knowledge, parental support and strong emotional maturity. Then the students will be able to take career according to their aptitude skills and desire. The Government, educational planners, curriculum designers, administrators and career guidance personnel should

prepare proper educational policies so that valuable time and potentialities of each individual can be used properly for his proper entry into right vocation. The present study will help the students take realistic approach to their vocational identity.

References

- Bala, I., Kaur, R., & Singh, S. (2017). Decision-making styles and academic achievement. *International Journal of Advanced Research and Development*, 2(4), 97-100
- Chaturvedi, S., & Khanna, S. (2005). A comparative study of career attitude of boys and girls of hindi medium higher secondary school students. *Journal of Educational Research*, 24(2), 5-12.
- Erikson, E. H. (1959). *Identity and the life cycle*. New York: International Universities Press.
- Erikson, E. H., & Erikson, J. M. (1997). *The life cycle completed: Extended version*. New York: Norton.
- Erikson, E. H., Erikson, J. M., & Kivnick, H. Q. (1986). *Vital involvement in old age*. New York: Norton.
- Gushue, G.V., & Kolone, R.L. (2006) The relationship of career decision making self-efficacy, vocational identity and career exploration behaviour in African American high school students. *Journal of Career Development*, 33, (1),19-28.
- Hargrove, B.K.,& Creagh, M.G.(2002). Family interaction patterns as predictors of vocational identity and career decision-making self-efficacy. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 4(1), 185-201
- Leundberg, S.A., Collie, W.C., Michael, J.S., & Richard, T.S. (1997). To study the theorized relation between vocational identity, and the concepts of consistency and differentiation. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, 45(2), 79-122.
- Skorikov, V. B., & Vondracek, F. W. (2007). *Vocational identity in career development in childhood and adolescence*. The Netherlands: Sense Publishers.
- Super,D.E.(1953). A theory of vocational development. *American Psychologist*, 8, 185-190.
- Wong, Zi Yang, and Kaur, Divjyot (2018) The role of vocational identity development and motivational beliefs in undergraduates' student engagement. *Counselling Psychology Quarterly*, 31 (3). pp. 294-316.[http:// doi: 10.1080/09515070.2017. 1314249](http://doi:10.1080/09515070.2017.1314249)

*** **